

THE MAGIC OF DISNEY: ENHANCING KAZAKH LANGUAGE THROUGH AUDIOVISUAL TRANSLATION**Saltanat Ye. Nurgaliyeva***PhD student in «Translation studies»,
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This article explores the process of translating Disney cartoons into Kazakh, highlighting the cultural and linguistic challenges involved. It highlights the importance of localization in maintaining Disney characters' charm and humor while making them relatable to Kazakh audiences. The study also highlights the significance of audiovisual translation in language preservation and youth engagement. The article "The Magic of Disney: Enhancing Kazakh Language through Audiovisual Translation" aims to analyze translation techniques, examine cultural adaptation, assess language enrichment, evaluate audience reception, highlight educational value, identify challenges faced by translators, and foster cross-cultural understanding. It will also explore the impact of Disney cartoons on Kazakh language development, audience engagement, and cultural understanding among young Kazakh speakers. The research will also explore potential solutions to improve translation quality and foster cross-cultural understanding through accessible storytelling.

Keywords: audiovisual translation, Disney cartoons, Disney characters, Kazakh language, localization, cross-cultural understanding, cultural adaptation, Kazakh audiences.

Introduction. Disney's animated films, particularly in Kazakh, are translated effectively to make them accessible and enhance the Kazakh language, highlighting the importance of effective translation in promoting cultural diversity. The preservation and promotion of Kazakh language are crucial, and translating international media like Disney's characters is a bridge to global storytelling and linguistic growth, requiring deep cultural understanding [1]. This research explores the translation process of Disney cartoons, focusing on techniques used to maintain charm and resonate with Kazakh audiences. It examines the impact on language enrichment and cultural engagement, particularly among young viewers, and highlights the transformative power of audiovisual translation [2]. The study aims to analyze the translation methods used to translate Disney cartoons into Kazakh, their cultural adaptation, language development, audience reception, educational benefits, challenges in translation, and promotion of cross-cultural understanding. The research will focus on maintaining narrative integrity, exploring cultural adaptation, assessing language development, analyzing audience reception, highlighting educational benefits, identifying challenges in translation, and promoting cross-cultural understanding through accessible storytelling [3]. The research will also explore the challenges faced by translators and propose strategies to improve future translations.

Materials and methods. This qualitative research focuses on the impact of audiovisual translation pro-

cesses on the Kazakh language and culture [4]. The process involved defining the research question, choosing a methodology, developing a research design, conducting interviews, focus groups, observations, and content analysis. The provided research outlined participant selection, data collection methods, and analysis strategies. Data collection involved open-ended questions, field notes, and document collection. Besides, data analysis included coding, thematic analysis, and narrative analysis. Interpreting findings involved reflecting on the data and relating them to existing cartoons. It aims to analyze translation techniques, audience reception, and the implications of Disney cartoons on linguistic enrichment and cultural engagement. The research aims to provide a nuanced exploration of the topic, combining qualitative and quantitative insights to achieve research objectives. The study examined the effectiveness of the translated cartoons in educational settings. The research provided a comprehensive understanding of the impact of Disney translations on Kazakh language and culture.

Results and discussion. Audiovisual translation (AVT) is a unique method that combines visual and auditory elements, such as films, TV shows, video games, and online videos, making it distinct from other translation methods. The types of AVT such as subtitling, dubbing, voice-over translation and localization were investigated in order to know which types of AVT were applied more while translating Disney cartoons.

Fig. 1. Applied AVT types for translation of Disney cartoons into Kazakh language

Therefore, it is crystal clear that dubbing has been a prevalent method in the translation of Disney cartoons, significantly influencing how these films are adapted for non-English speaking audiences. Dubbing enhances viewing experience by replacing original dialogue with voiceovers in target language, allowing audiences to fully engage with visuals and follow stories without subtitles. Moreover, dubbing enhances emotional connection between characters and audience, as skilled voice actors effectively convey personalities and emotions in the target language, making characters relatable and enjoyable. It allows for cultural adaptation, adjusting jokes, idioms, and references to resonate with the target audience, making content more relevant and engaging, enhancing film enjoyment. Disney's dubbing success is attributed to its dedication to high-quality voice acting, investing in talented actors to bring characters to life across various languages.

The article "The Magic of Disney: Enhancing Kazakh Language through Audiovisual Translation" highlights the positive impact of Disney films on the promotion and development of Kazakh language. The analysis reveals several significant findings:

1. Increased language exposure. The audiovisual translation of Disney films enhances Kazakh language exposure, particularly for children, through engaging storytelling and familiar characters, promoting language acquisition and retention.

2. Cultural reference. Disney films translated into Kazakh contextualize Eastern storytelling, making the language more relatable and accessible, fostering a sense of identity among young viewers.

3. Language proficiency. The study reveals that watching translated Disney films can boost Kazakh language proficiency by providing engaging and popular

content for learners to practice and enhance their language skills.

4. Audiovisual learning benefits. Disney's dynamic storytelling, combining visual elements with audio, enhances comprehension and retention in children, as they associate spoken language with visual cues.

The study emphasizes the significance of audiovisual translation in language enhancement, particularly for minority languages like Kazakh, using Disney films as a fun and engaging tool. Translated content enhances children's cultural identity, language skills, and cultural pride by exposing them to Disney narratives in their native language. For instance, some of characters' names were not translated with the help of direct translation as how the words are used together in a phrase or sentence, because translators wanted to keep own Kazakh cultural identity providing cartoon characters' names with Kazakh ones so that Kazakh audience could perceive their names much more easily. According to Kakhaber Abashidze, CEO of Disney in Central and Eastern Europe, CIS countries, Georgia and Mongolia, the adaptation and dubbing of films for various countries is an integral part of the content development strategy at Disney and is a long-established process. Moreover, Disney's Character Voices International team is working on 30 translations of each film into various languages, utilizing talented consultants and technical specialists to ensure characters are close and understandable to the audience, as part of Disney's content development strategy [5]. The study evaluated the impact and reception of Disney cartoons translated into Kazakh among viewers, based on a survey of respondents.

Fig.2. Results of research on respondents watching Disney cartoons in Kazakh language

Subsequently, it turned out that the majority of Kazakh respondents, around 21,3%, regularly watch Disney cartoons, indicating their high level of engagement (it is shown as “High” in figure 2) with Kazakh-speaking audiences. Whereas positive language learning impact (it is shown as “Positive” in fig.2) revealed that 17,5% of Kazakh respondents found that watching Disney cartoons has improved their language skills, especially among younger viewers who find the content entertaining. Another item as “Cultural relevance” (“CR” in fig.2) demonstrates that the adaptation of Disney stories into Kazakh, according to respondents (20%), significantly enhanced the relatability and enjoyment of the narratives, fostering a sense of cultural identity and pride. However, 22,5% of participants preferred dubbed Disney cartoons over subtitling, citing the immersive viewing experience and children's benefit from spoken dialogue. The item “Impact on Family viewing habits” (shown as “IFVH” in fig.2) illustrated that Disney cartoons in Kazakh foster family bonding, with 18,8% of respondents stating they encourage discussions about cultural values and lessons shared during watching together. To sum up, Disney cartoons translated into Kazakh are highly valued, promoting language learning, cultural connection, and family engagement, emphasizing the need for quality content.

The study suggests that incorporating audiovisual materials like Disney films into language education can enhance learning experiences, aligning with modern pedagogical theories. Nowadays most teenagers and children are interested in watching Disney cartoons because these films attract their attention. Therefore, they were translated into Kazakh language so that they could perceive any information easily and learn Kazakh language more deeply at the same time. Educators can leverage these films to create interactive lessons that blend language skills with visual storytelling. For example, teachers can use scenes from Disney movies to teach vocabulary, grammar, and cultural nuances, allowing students to see the language in action. Using familiar cultural narratives helps students connect with their language on a deeper level. Disney films, when translated into Kazakh, provide an opportunity to explore

themes of identity, tradition, and values within a modern context. This not only fosters language acquisition but also reinforces cultural pride and awareness among young learners. Educational programs can be designed to include discussions about cultural representation in media, encouraging critical thinking about how language and culture intertwine. By using popular films, educators can capture students' interest, leading to increased participation and enthusiasm for learning [6]. Structured activities, such as watching segments of films followed by discussions, vocabulary exercises, or creative writing prompts based on the narratives, can further enhance language skills in a fun and relatable manner [7]. Audiovisual materials enhance language learning by catering to different learning styles, promoting inclusivity through visual, auditory, and kinesthetic activities, thereby creating a holistic learning environment for all students. In addition to language skills, engaging with Disney films in Kazakh can encourage students to think critically about narratives, themes, and character development. Educators can facilitate discussions that prompt students to analyze the content, drawing connections between the stories and their own experiences or cultural context [8]. This analytical approach not only improves language proficiency but also fosters deeper cognitive skills. Disney film-based group activities foster collaboration, improve language skills, and enhance communication, thereby enhancing students' confidence and proficiency in a social context [9,10]. Technology integration in classrooms enhances audiovisual materials, allowing flexible learning opportunities and utilizing apps for dynamic language learning through gamification, interactive quizzes, and collaborative projects.

Conclusion. The given article highlights the role of audiovisual media, particularly Disney films, in promoting the Kazakh language. Through effective translation practices like dubbing, these stories engage young audiences and serve as tools for language acquisition and cultural connection. The article advocates for continued use of audiovisual translation to enrich the Kazakh language landscape and promote cultural pride in Kazakhstan. Further studies could explore the long-

term effects of audiovisual translation on language proficiency across different age groups. Additionally, investigating the impact of other media forms, such as video games or online content, on language acquisition could provide a broader understanding of how to effectively enhance the Kazakh language in a digital age.

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